

FEATURES OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF INTELLECTUAL AND CREATIVE COMPETENCE OF FUTURE TEACHERS

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Abstract. This article reveals the meaning of such concepts as intelligence, ingenuity, empathy in the development of intellectual and creative competence of future teachers. The concept of pedagogical communication and its role in the development of the intellectual and creative competence of future teachers are also revealed.

Keywords: pedagogical thinking, empathy, creative learning, pedagogical dialogue, communication.

ОСОБЕННОСТИ РАЗВИТИЯ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТУАЛЬНО-ТВОРЧЕСКОЙ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ БУДУЩИХ УЧИТЕЛЕЙ

Аннотация. В данной статье раскрывается значение таких понятий, как интеллект, сообразительность, эмпатия в развитии интеллектуально-творческой компетентности будущих педагогов. Также раскрывается понятие педагогическое общение и его роль в развитии интеллектуально-творческой компетентности будущих учителей.

Ключевые слова: педагогическое мышление, эмпатия, креативные тренинги, педагогическое общение, коммуникативность

INTRODUCTION

There are a number of specific features and conditions for the development of the intellectual and creative competence of future teachers. Among them are pedagogical intelligence, goodwill, and creative training.

Pedagogical ingenuity, intelligence can be equated with the most valuable personal, business and creative qualities. This quality can be acquired on the basis of patterns of perception by students and its evaluation by teachers. It became known that there are many information signs that are "indicators of specific personality traits" for the formation of the correct image of another person (student, classmate, colleague). These include physiological indicators, facial expressions, gestures, among them the characterological features of writing, color recognition, the type and technique of personal living, and the features of the interaction of interlocutors in communication. These include verbal and non-verbal components of pedagogical communication and human behavior, features of psychological types of accentuation[1].

It is not easy to become a smart teacher, but this quality can and should be developed by a teacher. The question arises about the method of development of pedagogical thinking of future teachers. In our opinion, work should begin with the collection and systematization of special knowledge about the psychology of students and the personality of a person as a whole, especially in the system of continuous education. However, we recommend that work on obtaining knowledge about a person be carried out in combination with theoretical and didactic education and practical experiments in order to directly study human nature. Of particular importance are modern knowledge from the fields of sociology, neuropsychology and synergetics. For example, studies conducted in recent years have shown that a teacher's personality type is an important factor in the development of a student's personality. Typology of personality depends on neuropsychological features, including the

characteristics of the human brain. Here we are talking about right-brained and left-brained people. For example, a left-brained teacher is better at assessing his left-brained students. Therefore, with a teacher, the student reveals the best aspects of his personality, becomes active, is not afraid of difficulties, and with a teacher of the opposite type, he becomes numb, frightened, loses self-confidence. The teacher, by virtue of his typological inclination, productively educates children belonging to "his" type, and, conversely, predominantly educates children belonging to the opposite type.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In modern domestic and foreign literature, you can find a lot of interesting tests for studying human nature with its specific features. However, the most effective exercises for developing the mind are experimental exercises. Speaking about the classical artifact about the influence of the first impression on the formation of the imagination, the question arises of an adequate perception of the modern pedagogical reality of the surrounding pedagogical reality. Therefore, along with the consolidation of theoretical knowledge, interesting experiments equip future teachers with the skills to quickly diagnose students by a combination of signs and indicators of individual characteristics.

The next step in the development of pedagogical consciousness is the analysis of specific cases presented in fiction, because "fiction has an inexhaustible supply of materials. Scientific psychology is unthinkable without them." [2]. When reading pedagogical situations in fiction and analyzing them, students indirectly work out the analytical techniques necessary for a smart teacher: comparison, historical-analytical thinking (when rereading individual passages in books), inductive-deductive thinking. Analysis of specific situations with carefully recorded images of characters sharpens professional ingenuity, quickness of thinking, the ability to foresee what is happening in the text, the student makes his choice, compares it with the decision of the situation in the text. Analysis of situations from fiction is the most important method for the development of the mind by entering the image of a hero. Learning to enter into such a literary image develops professional imagination, intuition, goodwill of future teachers.

To train the skills of empathy, observation and analysis, which are elements of pedagogical intelligence, students can fill the bank of exercises with fragments from practice, which can be pedagogical material for group learning in the form of pedagogical commercial games.

1. Here is an excerpt from the scenario of a commercial game on the topic "Mindfulness in the work of a teacher." The problem noticed and noted by the student trainees was that the children did not follow the usual hygiene standards. The task that was proposed to be solved during the game was to find out the reasons for students' non-compliance with simple hygiene rules and ways to eliminate them.
2. Stages of the game
 - 2.1. Exchanging opinions about the reasons for the appearance of "violation" in the group. The participants of the game were given the opportunity to express their expectations from the point of view of the organizer of educational activities, teachers, school psychologists, social pedagogues, etc.
 - 2.2. Fulfillment of the situation of solving this problem by students in a test way. Students participating in group teaching practice, parents of students, fellow teachers, directors present the results of the week during which they attended classes.

Students involved in the development of pedagogical thinking technology can acquire express diagnostic skills in a relatively short period of study, gain psychological self-confidence in choosing effective pedagogical means of teaching, educating and developing students.

The basis of training creative thinking is the unity and interaction of activity, personal and situational components. Psychological and pedagogical training is aimed at the formation and development of creative abilities. As a propensity to perceive new ideas, creativity is represented by the potential propensity to think, feel and act comprehensively. At the same time, the scientist M.M. Kashapov brings creativity to diversity and promotes innovation and sustainable development. This ability cannot be forced to develop, but its development can be maintained. [2,358 cnh.].

Measures of creativity include fluency, flexibility, originality, degree of sophistication, and detail in solutions. The main idea of creative training is to create opportunities for independence, student initiative, develop their sense of responsibility, the ability to creatively solve emerging problems, readiness for personal and professional development on a creative basis in the future.

The content of creative training is aimed at the formation of cognitive skills necessary for the formation of the creative qualities of the individual. The training forms an attitude to the subject and the pedagogical process as a means of self-development, which creates a fertile basis and soil for creativity. When learning is carried out as a creative research activity, it becomes a creative process for future student teachers.

The success of the training is determined by the mobile orientation of new things. Such stimulation of creativity contributes to the process of self-realization of the future teacher-student, the development of his abilities.

RESULTS

Creative training requires the following conditions: a) treating all answers, even the most unexpected, unusual and strange questions, as valuable and worthy of attention, i. there are no right or wrong answers; b) support students' desire to search for new heuristic answers; v) creating a welcoming environment through emotional mutual support; g) using the "discussion thread" as a tool for collective search for a new, unique/original solution to the problem under discussion.

The selection of exercises for creative learning should be based on an understanding of creative thinking as a gradual, consistent formation, the nature and characteristics of teachers' creativity as a developing and teaching quality. The first, preparatory stage in the development of creativity is represented by the formation of a system of concepts, the creation of a generalized image of the problem under study. This is the choice of the object of search: statement, presentation of the problem, task, question. In the activities of teachers, such questions and tasks always come from outside, in the form of professional requirements. However, according to many researchers studying the problems of pedagogical creativity, the main difference between an intellectually developed personality and a creative personality is that the former solves the tasks assigned to her, and the creative personality sees the need for a particular solution and independently solves problems. [3, 71-72 b.].

The ability to independently see the main problems and solve them requires the development of special qualities of perception, memory and thinking. Such qualities of perception as concreteness, analysis and predictability become the basis for the operational regulation of the teacher's creativity. When particularly complex tasks arise, the importance of such qualities as the amount of memory, the width of the associative chain, the flexibility of thinking and its fluency is also very important. For this reason, at the preparatory stage of preparing a creative training, it is necessary to work out processes that help to form the ability to independently see and set tasks, to choose exercises that help develop and determine the main direction of creativity.

The second, research stage of the creative process is provided by the development of a system of actions in the area under study, and this is achieved through the widespread use of problem-based learning. It develops creativity and independent thinking.

Finding an optimal, effective way to solve a problem situation, a new way of acting is traditionally associated with a heuristic, synthetic or unexpected form of thinking, i.e. with the work of the subconscious. The work of the subconscious is imprinted in the shell of the human brain, its images, fixed, have specific forms of existing operations. These are creative combinations that reconstruct reality and can be brought into consciousness while learning to be creative.

It is recommended to choose exercises aimed at developing the natural, creative functioning of our mind, that is, freedom of thinking, connecting unrelated events, phenomena, concepts, transferring tasks from one discipline / subject to another, developing creativity based on other principles. In other words, exercises at this stage of the development of creativity of future teachers should be aimed at eliminating stereotypes of thinking, including increasing the level of combinatorial work of thinking.

The third, implementation stage of the creative process leads to creativity and relies on the use of exploratory teaching methods to solve non-standard pedagogical problems. To implement this stage, it is necessary that future teachers have professional skills, that is, relevant professional competencies. For a teacher, these are the competencies of communication, organization, self-improvement, such as individual courage, independence, determination, independence from others, which are a very important requirement not only for the manifestation of creative originality, but also for mixing with the "creatogenic" qualities that define it [2, 331-390 b.].

Therefore, it is recommended to divide all didactic material into blocks for the development of creativity of future teachers. At the same time, it is required that the structure of each of them includes a brief description of a certain opportunity, test tasks, exercises and comments. This approach to the technological support for the development of creativity makes it possible to understand the mechanism of its formation and to carry out targeted training.

DISCUSSION

The practice of creativity should be done as an intellectual exercise every day. Therefore, voluntary regulation becomes relevant. In addition, for the development of the creative Self, it is absolutely necessary to use the methods of continuous registration of daily achievements in the development of human creatogenic qualities.

When creative training is done in a group, brainstorming (cooperative thinking and discussion) has proven to be effective in creating a creative environment. The essence of this methodological technique is that a group of students develops and creates as many ideas as possible without expressing a critical opinion about other members of the creative group. Another way to activate collective creativity - synectics - is essentially close to the brainstorming method. Elements of criticism can be allowed here, and all four methods based on analogy must be observed: direct, personal sympathy, symbolic and fantastic.

The use of methods of collective creativity allows revealing the deep creative reserves of future teachers. Although these methods cannot replace experience, knowledge, skills, they help to increase the power of thought, help to think "freely and without restrictions." [4].

Communicativeness, that is, accessibility to communication, as the most important component of the teacher's creative readiness, can be expressed by a combination of three main

communicative functions: influence (formation), organization (motivation) and information transfer. [5, 51 b.]

Under the development of certain methods and methods of preparing future teachers for professional communication, researcher V. A. Kan-Kalik understands the approval and selection of forms and methods of communicative training developed in social psychology, theater pedagogy and psychotherapy [6.]. Communication as a pedagogical category is considered from three interrelated positions. In accordance with them, pedagogical communicative training is carried out: attracting future teacher-students to socio-cultural and pedagogical values that form the humanistic orientation of the individual; development of the creative individuality of the teacher.

CONCLUSIONS

Therefore, the selection of exercises for the development of communication skills is based on the patterns of the communicative process and the principles of verbal communication. Accordingly, he must be able to practice professional, i.e. purposeful and internally conditioned interactions with students using verbal means and non-verbal components.

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